

Impact & Next Steps

- ✓ Better Welfare
- ✓ Higher Efficiency
- ✓ Early Health Detection
- ✓ Sustainable Farming
- ✓ Robotic Intelligence

Current Status

- Initial Integration
- Lab Validation
- Cloud Platform
- Multi-module Setup

Contact Us:

www.dairy40.eu

info@dairy40.eu

Follow us on social media!

@dAIry40

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

dairy_{4.0}

Advanced, trustworthy
AI and data solutions
for individualised
automated milking &
feeding of dairy cows

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

Integrated Robot v1

From Sensors to Decision

Vision Sensors + Milk Analysis

Animal Status Classifier

Cloud Platform

Data Platform & Digital Twin

The dAlry 4.0 Cloud Platform

- ✓ Unified Farm data
- ✓ Interoperability
- ✓ Automated Alerts

Digital Twin Dashboard

- Activity & Health
- Production trends
- Feeding simulations

Health aspect 1

Health aspect 2

Health aspect 3

Health aspect 4

Vision Module

Advanced Sensing & AI

Milk Quality Analysis

Optical Analysis (Spectroscopy)

Molecules

Protein

Spectrum

Data

Vision Cameras

Optical Milk Analysis

AI Models

per animal insights

Cloud-based Integration

Animal Status Classifier

DSS

Simulator

Farm Management Decision